

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISATION DATA AND PROPERTIES OF CHROMIUM (III) CHELATES

Complex	Cr(%)	N(%)	Cl/C (%)	S/H (%)	H ₂ O(%)	Λ_M	${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$
[Cr(L) ₃].4H ₂ O	6.5	5.8	61.7*	3.9*	3.9	(a) 95	17.5 kK
green; $\mu = 3.7$ B.M.	(6.8)	(5.6)	(62.0)	(4.2)	(4.2)	(c) 3	
[Cr(L)(<i>o</i> -phen)(tu) ₂]Cl ₂	8.0	15.0	11.3	9.2	—	(a) 79	18.1
dirty green; $\mu = 3.6$ B. M.	(7.8)	(14.7)	(10.6)	(9.6)	—	(b) 149	
[Cr(L)(dipy)(tu) ₂]Cl ₂	8.2	15.0	11.3	9.7	—	(a) 87	18.5
brown; $\mu = 3.6$ B.M.	(8.1)	(15.2)	(11.0)	(9.9)	—	(b) 168	
[Cr(L) ₂ (<i>o</i> -phen)]L	5.7	8.3	—	—	—	(a) 97	19.2
snuff; $\mu = 3.8$ B. M.	(6.0)	(8.1)	—	—	—		

Figures in parentheses indicate calculated values; * carbon and hydrogen; Λ_M in ohms⁻¹cm²mol⁻¹; (a) 0.001 M in methanol; (b) 0.0005 M in methanol, (c) 0.001 M in nitromethane.

[Cr(L)(*o*-phen)(tu)₂]Cl₂: This was prepared by following a procedure similar to that described above.

[Cr(L)₂(*o*-phen)]L: 0.4 gm (~0.0005 mol) of [Cr(L)₃].4H₂O was added to a hot alcoholic solution of 0.1 gm (~0.0005 mol) of *o*-phenanthroline and refluxed for 1 hr. The colour of the solution changed from green to snuff and some crystals started separating out. The mixture was allowed to crystallise in air for a day. The crystals were collected, washed with acetone and stored in a desiccator.

Analyses and physical methods: Chromium was estimated iodometrically after oxidising to Cr(VI) by fusion with Na₂O₂ and NaOH. Chloride and sulphur were estimated gravimetrically as AgCl and BaSO₄ respectively after fusion with Na₂O₂ and Na₂CO₃. Nitrogen was estimated by Duma's combustion technique. Carbon and hydrogen determinations as also the ir spectra were run at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Magnetic susceptibility was determined by Gouy method using CuSO₄. 5H₂O, as the calibrant. Nujol mull electronic spectra were run at R.S.I.C., Madras. Results are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

2(*o*-Hydroxyphenyl) benzooxazole reacts with *tris* (thiourea) chromium(III) chloride to give a homo-ligand complex [Cr(L)₃]. The complex is solvolyzed in methanol to a 1:1 electrolyte ($\Lambda_M \sim 95$ ohms⁻¹cm²mol⁻¹). In nitromethane, however, the complex is a non-electrolyte ($\Lambda_M \sim 3$ ohms⁻¹cm²mol⁻¹). In view of the solvolytic nature proportionate amount of *o*-phenanthroline was added to a hot alcoholic solution of the homo-complex [Cr(L)₃]. The resulting mixed chelate, [Cr(L)₂(*o*-phen)]L, was identified by chemical analysis and Λ_M value of 97 ohms⁻¹cm²mol⁻¹ in methanol. A reaction of [Cr(tu)₃]Cl₃ first with *o*-phenanthroline/dipyridyl and then with benzooxazole furnished [Cr(L)(*o*-phen/dipy)(tu)₂]Cl₂. Conductance data of [Cr(L)(dipy)(tu)₂]Cl₂ and [Cr(L)(*o*-phen)(tu)₂]Cl₂ in methanol indicate substantial ion-pairing even at 0.001 M level.

The electronic spectra of the above complexes exhibit bands at 520-570 nm and around 410 nm. These bands are assigned to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ transitions respectively. The first transition gives a measure of 10 *Dq* value. The magnetic moments are those expected for a *d*³ system (3.5-3.8 B.M.).

The ir spectrum of the ligand reveals strong and medium bands at 1630 cm⁻¹ and 1410 cm⁻¹ corresponding to C=N and phenolic-OH vibration. In the complexes the C=N stretch is substantially lowered to around 1605 cm⁻¹ while the 1410 cm⁻¹ band is absent. In the mixed ligand complexes characteristic bands due to dipyridyl and *o*-phenanthroline are observed^{10,11}.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the University Grants Commission for financial assistance.

References

1. T. R. HARKINS, J. L. WALTER, O. E. HARRIS and H. FREISER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 260.
2. E. J. DUFF and M. N. HUGHES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 477.
3. E. J. DUFF, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 310.
4. M. V. ARTEMENKO, E. A. CHISTAKOVA, K. F. SLYUSARENKO and O. B. PRITULA, *Chem. Abs.*, 1972, **76**, 120979s.
5. L. V. SUPRINA, A. V. GAMOVSKII, Y. V. KOLODYARZHNYI and O. A. OSIPOV, *Chem. Abs.*, 1972, **76**, 80393.
6. J. E. HOUSE (JR.) and P. K. LAU, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 223.
7. L. A. TEVZADZO, A. D. GARNOVSKII, N. I. PIRTISKHALOVA, O. A. OSIPOV and L. I. KUZNETSOVA, *Chem. Abs.*, 1975, **82**, 92422h.
8. J. L. WALTER and H. FREISER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1952, **24**, 984.
9. M. M. KHAN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 1621.
10. R. L. DUTTA and S. P. BANERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 497.
11. R. L. DUTTA and A. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1980, **42**, 1205.

Substituted Malonato Chromium(III) Complexes

S. MODAK, P. K. DAS and B. CHAKRAVARTY*

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235, West Bengal

Manuscript received 3 October 1980, accepted 11 August 1981

TRIS-malonato⁻¹⁻⁴ and methylmalonato⁻⁵ and also isomeric forms of diaquobismalonato^{-6,7} and diaquobismethylmalonato⁻⁵ chromium (III) complexes have been prepared by different workers and all these complexes were employed in mechanistic investiga-

tions⁵⁻¹². Utilization of these complexes in mechanistic studies necessitates the syntheses of other *tris*- and *diaquobis*-substituted malonato complexes with the view that these complexes may be utilized for deep insight study into the mechanisms. In this communication we report the syntheses of several of these *tris*- and *diaquobis*-substituted malonato-chromium(III) complexes.

Preparation of Complexes :

Potassium trisethylmalonatochromate(III) : The ethylmalonato complex was prepared by a modified method of Lapraik¹ used in the preparation of *tris*-malonato complex. Chromic hydroxide, Cr(OH)₃, was precipitated from a solution of chromic salt with just sufficient potassium hydroxide and washed repeatedly with water until it was free from the anion. Equivalent amount of ethylmalonic acid, dissolved in a little amount of water, was added to the precipitated chromic hydroxide and the mixture heated on a water bath for 1-1½ hrs with occasional stirring. The solution was filtered, cooled and a slight excess of potassium carbonate was added, followed by ethanol and ether to precipitate the crystals. These were filtered, recrystallized and dried in air.

Potassium trisdimethylmalonatochromate(III) and potassium trisbenzylmalonatochromate(III) tetrahydrate : Preparation of both of these complexes were made with some modification of the above method. Stoichiometric amounts of respective acids were added to a little excess of the precipitated chromic hydroxide and the mixture was vigorously stirred at 40-45° for 3-4 hrs. It was then filtered from unreacted Cr(OH)₃ and treated with potassium carbonate, little by little, until the whole solution was neutral. The complexes could not be isolated from the aqueous solutions by adding organic solvents like alcohols acetone or ether as both these complexes were soluble in these organic solvents. The complex solutions were slowly evaporated for crystallization. The crystals were recrystallized from aqueous solutions.

Cis- and trans- Potassium diaquobisethylmalonatochromate(III) : Isomeric forms of this complex were

prepared by the method used by Hamm and Perkins⁶ in the preparation of corresponding malonato complex. *Cis*- isomer forms violet crystals and the *trans*- isomer forms reddish-violet crystals.

Cis- and trans- Potassium diaquobisdimethylmalonatochromate(III) and cis- and trans- Potassium diaquobenzylmalonatochromate(III) : These complexes were also prepared by a modification of Hamm and Perkins' method. Chromic hydroxide was precipitated from an aqueous solution of a chromic salt (chloride or nitrate) with just sufficient potassium hydroxide. The chromic hydroxide thus obtained was washed and treated with twice the equivalent amount of the respective malonic acid and an equivalent amount of potassium hydroxide in about 100 ml of water. The mixture was then maintained at 40-50° with vigorous stirring for a day or two. It was filtered from any unreacted chromic hydroxide and evaporated slowly in a crystallization dish in a vacuum desiccator. Reddish-violet crystals of the *trans*- form appeared on the dish within 2-3 days. The crystals were recrystallized from aqueous solutions in usual manner.

Violet crystals of the *cis*- isomer were obtained when the same solutions were evaporated rapidly in a rotary evaporator instead of evaporating slowly in a desiccator. However, the *cis*- isomers obtained in this manner were mixed with some *trans*- isomers. As these higher substituted malonato complexes were soluble in organic solvents, these isomers could not be obtained with organic solvents as employed in the separation of isomeric forms of diaquobismalonato complexes. Yield in both the cases were generally poor.

All these complexes are stable in air and aqueous solutions. The analytical, conductance (in aqueous solution) and electronic spectral data of the complexes are presented in Table I. Water of crystallization of these complexes were determined by heating the complexes in an air oven at 105° for about an hour. *Cis*-structure of the diaquobisethylmalonato complex was based on the fact that this complex species reacted with a mol of the bidentate ligand, ethylmalonate ion, to give the *tris*- complex with the replacement of two aquo-ligands. The *trans*- structures of the *trans*-

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, ELECTRICAL CONDUCTANCE AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	Found* (Calcd), %			Δ_m Ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	ν_{max} (ε)cm ⁻¹	
	Cr	C	H		I	II
1. K ₃ [Cr(Etmal) ₃]	9.38 (9.20)	31.73 (31.87)	4.05 (4.25)	454	17.09 (55)	23.70 (52)
2. K ₃ [Cr(Me ₂ mal) ₃]	9.31 (9.20)	31.70 (31.87)	4.19 (4.25)	451	17.24 (47)	23.26 (45)
3. K ₃ [Cr(Benzylmal) ₃].4H ₂ O	6.11 (6.01)	40.90 (41 60)	4.00 (3 70)	432	17.12 (57)	23.26 (51)
4. <i>cis</i> K[Cr(Etmal) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₁]	12.99 (13.30)	29.89 (30.70)	5.46 (5.12)	137	17.12 (19)	23.75 (18)
5. <i>trans</i> K[Cr(Etmal) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₁]	13.21 (13.30)	31.14 (30.70)	5.24 (5.12)	142	17.39 (20)	23.92 (19)
6. <i>trans</i> K[Cr(Me ₂ mal) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₁]	12.79 (13.30)	29.88 (30.70)	5.00 (5.12)	124	17.54 (18)	23.92 (18)
7. <i>trans</i> K[Cr(Benzylmal) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₁]	9.85 (9.58)	44.11 (44.20)	3.50 (3.68)	136	17.61 (40)	23.81 (34)

*Estimations of C and H were done by Prof. H. Malissa and G. Reuter, Analytical Laboratory, 0-5250, Engelskirchen, W. Germany.

complexes have been tentatively assigned from the colour similarities of these complexes with that of *trans*-diaquobismalonato-⁶ and *trans*-diaquobismethylmalonato-⁵ complexes.

Molar conductances in aqueous solution of the complexes indicated that the *tris*-complexes were tri-univalent in nature while the diaquobis-complexes were uni-univalent in nature. Molar conductance values of all the complexes are also given in Table 1.

The electronic spectra of all these complexes showed two bands. The lower energy band may be assigned to the transition ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ and the higher energy band to ${}^4T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ transition. Both the bands were well defined but the extinctions were usually small.

References

1. W. LAPRAIK, *Chem. News*, 1893, 67, 219.
2. F. M. JAEGER, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1919, 38, 171.
3. H. T. S. BRITTON and M. E. D. JARRETT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1728.
4. T. N. SRIVASTAVA and S. P. AGRAWAL, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1958, 6, 58.
5. J. C. CHANG, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1974, 34, 221.
6. R. E. HAMM, and R. H. PERKINS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 2083.
7. J. C. CHANG, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, 30, 945.
8. D. BANERJEA and C. CHATTERJEE, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, 30, 3354.
9. D. BANERJEA and C. CHATTERJEE, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1967, 29, 2387.
10. J. C. CHANG, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, 32, 1402.
11. J. C. CHANG, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1973, 35, 2417.
12. E. MANTOVANI and C. FURLANI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1969, 31, 1213.

Complexes of Some Bivalent Metals with 4-Amino-5-Oxo-3-Thioxo-6-Benzyl-2,3,4,5-Tetrahydro-1,2,4-Triazine and Its Derivatives

P. D. SINGH and L. K. MISHRA*

Department of Chemistry, Science College Patna-800 005

Manuscript received 11 November 1980, revised 23 July 1981, accepted 11 August 1981

4-Amino-5-oxo-3-thioxo-6-benzyl-2, 3, 4, 5-tetrahydro-1,2,4-triazine (BTH) and its 6-*o*-chlorobenzyl (CBTH) and 6-*p*-methoxybenzyl (MBTH) derivatives (shown below) are multidentate

(X = benzyl, *o*-chlorobenzyl or *p*-methoxybenzyl)

ligands but their complexes with metal ions are not known. In present communication the preparation and characterisation of complexes of these ligands with Ni(II), Co(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) are reported.

Experimental

BTH, CBTH and MBTH were prepared by method of Dornov¹ and uv, ir and magnetic susceptibilities were measured as reported earlier².

Preparation of complexes; ML_2 ($M = \text{Co}^{2+}$, Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , or Cd^{2+} and $LH = \text{BTH}$, MBTH or CBTH): A methanolic solution of hydrated metal(II) chloride (acetate in case of Cd^{2+} and Zn^{2+}) was added with stirring to the ligand dissolved in hot methanol (1:2 metal to ligand molar ratio) containing 6–7 g of sodium acetate. The resulting solution was refluxed on a steam bath for about 20–30 mins and diluted with an excess of water when neutral *bis* chelate separated out as a flocculent precipitate. In some cases the complex separated immediately on mixing the reactants. The products were filtered, washed with water and methanol and dried at 120°.

$Ni(\text{MBT})_2$; (*Orange-red form*): Methanolic solution of hydrated Ni(II) chloride was refluxed with stoichiometric proportion of the ligand dissolved in pyridine-dioxane mixture. The resulting solid product was removed and the filtrate was diluted with excess of water when a flocculent orange-red product separated.

$Ni(\text{LH})_2\text{Cl}_2$; ($LH = \text{BTH}$ and MBTH): Stoichiometric proportion of the ligand was suspended in methanolic solution of hydrated nickel(II) chloride (1.2 g in 100 ml) and refluxed on a steam bath for about 1 hr. The resulting solution was concentrated to a small volume and the complex was separated by adding excess of ether. The product was filtered and washed thoroughly with ether and dried in a desiccator over CaCl_2 .

$\text{Cu}(\text{LH})\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$; ($LH = \text{BTH}$, CBTH and MBTH); $\text{Cu}(\text{BTH})\text{Br}_2 \cdot Y$; ($Y = \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ or $\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{O}_2$) and $\text{Cu}(\text{BTH})\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{O}_2$: Stoichiometric proportion of methanolic solution of appropriate cupric halide (0.005 mole) was added to the ligand dissolved in hot methanol with stirring. On cooling the resulting solution, solvated complex separated as a fine crystalline product. The product was filtered washed with methanol and dried in air. The dioxane solvated complex was obtained when the preparation was carried out in dioxane-methanol mixture.

Results and Discussion

In alkaline medium these ligands are deprotonated and form inner bischelates and analytical results of the dried samples correspond with the formula $[ML_2]$ [$M = \text{Co}(\text{II})$, $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$, $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$, $\text{Zn}(\text{II})$ or $\text{Cd}(\text{II})$ and $LH = \text{BTH}$, MBTH or CBTH]. The analytical results of dihalo complexes $\text{Cu}(\text{LH})\text{X}_2 \cdot Z$ [$X = \text{Cl}$ or Br and $Z = \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ or dioxane] and $\text{Ni}(\text{LH})_2\text{Cl}_2$ [$LH = \text{BTH}$ or MBTH] are also in good agreement of the suggested formulae. The methanolic solutions of dihalo complexes $\text{Ni}(\text{LH})_2\text{Cl}_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{LH})\text{X}_2 \cdot Z$ display negligible conductance value (Λ_m 10–20 $\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}\text{cm}^2$) indicating that halogen atoms are coordinated to metal atom in these complexes.

As usual Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes are diamagnetic and do not display electronic reflectance band in the visible region. Excepting $\text{Cu}(\text{BT})_2$ which is diamagnetic, other inner bischelates of copper(II)